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THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS, ESSENCE, CONTENT AND FORMS OF ECONOMIC EDUCATION FOR STUDENTS OF GRADES 5-6 OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Turakhanov Oybek Davlatalievich

Deputy Dean for Academic Affairs, Faculty of Economics,
 Namangan State University

Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical foundations, essence, content, and forms of economic education for students of grades 5–6 in secondary schools. The study emphasizes the importance of popularizing economic knowledge among young people within the educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account both national and international experiences. The article examines the key tasks of economic education, such as the rational use of money and resources, financial literacy, basic business principles, and the formation of a labor culture. Additionally, it compares the roles of the family, school, and society in economic education, integrating the perspectives of Eastern thinkers and contemporary scholars. As a result, effective methodological approaches are proposed for fostering economic awareness among students of grades 5–6.

Key words: Economic education, financial literacy, labor culture, business principles, secondary schools, students, education system of Uzbekistan, effective use of resources.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada umumta'lim maktablarining 5–6-sinf o'quvchilariga iqtisodiy tarbiya berishning nazariy asoslari, mohiyati, mazmuni va shakllari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda O'zbekiston Respublikasining ta'lim siyosatida iqtisodiy bilimlarni yoshlar o'rtasida ommalashtirishning ahamiyati, shuningdek, milliy va xalqaro tajribalar yoritilgan. Maqolada iqtisodiy tarbiyaning asosiy vazifalari – pul va resurslardan oqilona foydalanish, moliyaviy savodxonlik, ishbilarmonlik asoslari hamda mehnat madaniyatini shakllantirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, oila, maktab va jamiyatning iqtisodiy tarbiyadagi o'rni, jumladan, Sharq mutafakkirlari va zamonaviy olimlarning qarashlari taqqosiy tahlil qilinadi. Natijada, 5–6-sinf o'quvchilarida iqtisodiy ongni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan samarali metodik yondashuvlar taklif etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Iqtisodiy tarbiya, moliyaviy savodxonlik, mehnat madaniyati, ishbilarmonlik asoslari, umumta'lim maktablari, o'quvchilar, O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi, resurslardan samarali foydalanish.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются теоретические основы, сущность, содержание и формы экономического образования учащихся 5–6 классов общеобразовательных школ. В исследовании подчеркивается важность популяризации экономических знаний среди молодежи в контексте образовательной политики Республики Узбекистан, а также учитывается национальный и международный опыт. Рассматриваются основные задачи экономического образования: рациональное использование денежных средств и ресурсов, финансовая грамотность, основы предпринимательства и формирование культуры труда. Кроме того, сопоставляется роль семьи, школы и общества в процессе экономического воспитания, включая взгляды восточных мыслителей и современных ученых. В результате предлагаются эффективные методические подходы к формированию экономического сознания у учащихся 5–6 классов.

Ключевые слова: Экономическое образование, финансовая грамотность, культура труда, принципы бизнеса, общеобразовательные школы, учащиеся, система образования Узбекистана, эффективное использование ресурсов.

INTRODUCTION

Economic education plays a crucial role in familiarizing young people with the economic system of society, its operational principles, and patterns of financial behavior. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the development of economic knowledge and skills among youth has become an integral part of state policy. In particular, establishing the theoretical foundations for providing economic education to students in grades 5–6 of secondary schools is aimed at fostering independent decision-making and life competencies grounded in economic understanding for their future development.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Economic education serves to shape the economic consciousness of the younger generation and to develop essential skills such as productive labor and the rational use of money and resources. This process is implemented by teaching students how to apply economic knowledge not only in theory but also in practice.

In Uzbekistan, the Law “On Education,” adopted on 2019-12-26, emphasizes the integration of economic knowledge into general education schools. The law sets forth objectives such as enhancing the quality of education, equipping students with modern knowledge, and fostering independent thinking.

Uzbek scholars, including economist Shavkat Tillo oglu, underline the significance of economic education in developing young people’s economic understanding: “Introducing young people to economic education serves to form their economic freedom and independent thinking.” Similarly, experts in higher education and scientific research, such as economist and education specialist Ma’murjon Karimov, stress that “Economic education helps young people adapt to the global economic system and prepares them for international economic competition.”

At this point, it can be stated with confidence that economic education lessons for students in grades 5–6 should primarily focus on the following key topics:

1. Economic concepts and terms – Introducing students to fundamental economic terms such as money, funds, resources, supply and demand, and economic efficiency.
2. Financial skills – Teaching financial practices such as budgeting, saving, and personal finance planning.
3. Business fundamentals – Explaining basic principles of entrepreneurship and small business development.
4. Effective use of resources – Emphasizing the rational management of various resources, including time and labor.

The Resolution of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Measures to Improve the System of Economic Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan,” adopted in 2022, provides a legal and strategic foundation for the development of economic education.^[1] This resolution outlines measures for the effective organization of economic education classes in schools and the modernization of teaching methods aimed at enhancing students’ practical economic competencies.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Providing economic education to students in grades 5–6 of secondary schools is a key task in developing their economic consciousness and cultivating independent thinking. Economic knowledge is not only a foundation of economic freedom for young people but also a prerequisite for making effective and informed decisions in the future. In this regard, the education system of Uzbekistan and its ongoing reforms, along with the approaches developed by economists and education specialists, hold particular significance.

Economic education is one of the crucial elements in raising a well-rounded individual. As Islam Karimov stated: “The fact that we prioritize economic transformation, completely reject the administrative-command distribution system, and base social relations on a market economy is a clear expression of our firm approach to reforming society.” Indeed, reforming society in accordance with the requirements of a market economy necessitates the development of economic thinking among its population. Therefore, fostering economic thinking in the younger generation is essential.

Economic education instills in students such skills as thrift, diligence, initiative, business acumen, economic calculation, and the ability to reflect critically. Eastern thinkers paid great attention to the content of economic education. Muhammad Ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi emphasized that mathematics plays a key role in human life, arguing that a person must understand arithmetic and be skilled in applying it. Only then can one evaluate the results of their labor using measurable indicators.

Abu Nasr al-Farabi noted that humans require numerous things for survival and must rely on others for their production, highlighting the necessity of economic communication. This idea resonates strongly in today’s globalized world, where economic integration leads to prosperity. In his work *On the Achieving of Happiness*, Al-Farabi wrote: “A person must know how to spend money wisely. Excessive stinginess results from miserliness, while unplanned spending leads to recklessness.”

These ideas from past scholars reflect the importance of expanding students’ economic thinking in both school and family environments by teaching thrift, business sense, and economic reasoning based on life experience. Economic education begins at home. When a child starts school, they begin to receive more structured knowledge in this domain. Abu Ali Ibn Sina emphasized this in his works, noting: “Family members must prepare in advance enough food for the day. Everyone should know how to store wheat, rice, and fruits. One must be economical with necessities. Parents must teach children not to waste money through guidance from an early age.”

Ibn Sina also asserted that children should be taught a trade to prepare them for life: “A person must thoroughly learn a trade, as it provides the means for future livelihood.” Mastery of a trade fosters independence in youth. In this process, children develop calculation skills and entrepreneurial attitudes. Parents may organize children’s involvement in yard work, cooking, laundry, repairs, and household maintenance. However, tasks should be assigned considering the child’s physical, intellectual, and emotional capacity. Parents should also supervise and support the child’s efforts, offering guidance and encouragement as needed.

The effectiveness of education depends significantly on the combined efforts of the family, school, community, and labor collectives, as well as the consistency of their expectations toward students. The youth of today will be tasked with addressing the critical challenges of the late 21st and early 22nd centuries. Therefore, it is vital to cultivate in them the ability to solve personal and societal problems, address national and international issues, and face the unpredictability of nature with resourcefulness and responsibility.^[3]

Students are introduced to the economic laws of Uzbekistan through natural sciences. In social studies classes, they explore the economic steps necessary for enhancing public welfare. In chemistry and biology lessons, teachers illustrate the economic benefits of mineral fertilizers with real-world examples. Students also investigate new technologies, their application in industry, and the economic value of scientific discoveries through both classroom and extracurricular activities.

A wide range of economic education objectives is achieved through labor education classes. The more engaging and practical these lessons are, the more effective they become in building students’ economic knowledge and skills. It is crucial that these lessons are content-rich and appropriately structured. In elementary education, economic concepts are integrated into reading, natural sciences, mathematics, and labor education. Students learn about the environment, labor, human life, the market, and pricing mechanisms. Elementary mathematics also develops logical and quantitative thinking, which is foundational for understanding market relations.

Labor lessons should serve as a bridge between theoretical economic knowledge and real-life application. For example, students create items from paper, cardboard, clay, and plasticine, using measured dimensions. They learn why these items are necessary, and how waste materials can be repurposed into useful products. These lessons teach thrift, entrepreneurship, and problem-solving skills.

In higher grades, lessons include topics such as “Development of Production Technology,” “Product Cost,” and “Foreign Trade Methods.” These subjects make a lasting impression when taught through real-life examples. To enhance economic education, comprehensive and purposeful objectives should be set, including:

- In economic geography lessons, offering deeper insights into concepts like “Foreign Economic Relations of Uzbekistan” and “Interregional Economic Cooperation.”
- Assigning textbook exercises that include economic analysis and tasks tied to real professions and economic sectors.

Extracurricular activities also offer ample opportunities for economic education. In geography clubs, students learn about national and regional development, labor organization, product quality, and environmental sustainability. These concepts deepen their understanding of Uzbekistan’s economic structure and guide them in identifying future career paths.

Economic education methods are diverse and may include discussions, lectures, hands-on activities, field trips to production sites, comparative analysis, and applied calculations. To nurture creative economic thinking, both curricular and extracurricular strategies should be used effectively. Teachers must continuously assess and monitor students’ progress in economic education.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Labor has always been, and continues to be, the foundation of human life and well-being. It is a fundamental obligation for all citizens, as it represents the primary means to achieve a prosperous and meaningful existence. Labor may be defined as the time, mental and physical effort, or purposeful activity expended by individuals to attain specific goals. Without labor, life is unsustainable. All living beings must consume in order to survive – from insects to birds, aquatic organisms to large mammals – none can live without nourishment. Humans, unlike other creatures, not only consume but also dress, build homes, trade, read, and create. All of these activities require resources, particularly money, as the essential medium of exchange and survival. In order to earn money and meet their needs, individuals must work. It is only through labor that food, clothing, and other essentials are produced. Labor not only enriches life materially but also enhances human dignity and shapes one’s future.

The primary objectives of labor education include the following:

1. To cultivate interest in, and appreciation for, various forms of labor – as these qualities are foundational to the success of labor education.

2. To develop a positive attitude towards labor among students.
3. To equip students with essential labor-related knowledge, practical skills, and competencies.
4. To foster students' interest in specific professions and assist them in career selection.^[6]

In shaping the content of labor education, a differentiated approach must be taken to address the diverse needs and abilities of students. The family plays a pivotal role in preparing young people for work and life, and assumes a key responsibility on behalf of society in instilling a strong work ethic.

For centuries, our ancestors have glorified labor and served as models of diligence. The vast intellectual, artistic, and architectural heritage they left – from scholarly manuscripts to majestic monuments – stands as testimony to their hard work. Great historical figures such as Al-Khwarizmi, Ibn Sina, Ismail al-Bukhari, Mirzo Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, and Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, all of whom made invaluable contributions to global science and culture, achieved success through their perseverance. They consistently advocated for labor and called upon youth to embrace diligence.

Labor education occupies a central place in the enlightening works of Central Asian thinkers, scholars, and poets. For example, the great Uzbek poet Alisher Navoi regarded hard work as a defining trait of true humanity. He extolled labor as a source of personal refinement and urged young people to work with enthusiasm and purpose. Likewise, Mirzo Ulugbek, a prominent figure in Eastern culture, emphasized the importance of educating youth about nature, its preservation, and the wise and measured use of its resources. He advocated for experiential learning – that students should draw conclusions through direct observation and develop conviction through personal understanding.

The enlighteners placed particular importance on labor education in youth upbringing. In their works, they expressed – often in poetic and inspirational language – that qualities such as curiosity, thrift, solidarity, and humanity could be cultivated through productive labor. They encouraged young people to acquire a trade or engage in meaningful work suited to their interests and aptitudes, insisting that a hardworking individual will never be dependent on others.

Young people were also advised to appreciate the value of human-made goods and to avoid wastefulness. Folk literature, too, contains countless wise proverbs and parables condemning idleness and glorifying productivity. Labor is not only a necessity for physical survival and material success but also a powerful tool for developing moral and spiritual values. It combats laziness, nurtures a sense of purpose, and contributes to overall well-being. Artistic works often emphasize that even the wealthiest individuals cannot find fulfillment without engaging in meaningful work. Nations, too, achieve progress through labor, which is the most critical driver of social advancement and noble aspirations.

The issue of labor education has consistently held a distinguished position in the heritage of enlightenment. Enlighteners urged youth to work for the benefit of society and emphasized the role of educators and parents in instilling these values. One of Uzbekistan's foremost educators, Abdulla Avloni, highlighted the importance of mastering a single trade during youth. In his work *Turkiy Guliston yoki Axloq*, he condemned laziness and praised initiative, writing:

“Our health, happiness, wealth, satisfaction, patience, virtue – our entire life – depends on movement. Those who are inactive are deprived of everything, are constantly dependent on others, and live in humiliation.”

Avloni advocated that children should learn a trade, that the elderly should remain engaged in productive activities, and that disdain for work, such as saying “coal mining or blacksmithing is not suitable for me,” only to remain idle, is a great sin. Young people who acquire a trade early in life will secure their place in society and avoid hardship.

The Wisdom of Labor and Its Educational Role

A well-known ancestral proverb states: “Forty trades are too few for a young man.” Among these trades are carpenter, painter, potter, jeweler, shoemaker, and baker. A person must learn the value of work from early childhood, master a profession that aligns with their interests, and strive to become a diligent individual. Across nations, those who are skilled in their craft are respected and admired – their profession, like a blossoming flower, enhances their identity. Work, whether physically demanding or relatively simple, has no moral quality in itself – it is neither inherently good nor bad. If one performs a task considered menial by others with genuine enthusiasm and dedication, it becomes a meaningful and satisfying pursuit. Such work, when done with love and intention, appears clean, voluntary, and attractive. Observers often say: “Thanks to his father – his hand is like a flower.” This phrase symbolizes a person whose daily labor, performed with humility and precision, defines moral virtue and social value.

Content and System of Labor Education for Primary School Students

Labor education begins in the family and continues through the school system, student organizations, and participation in community and production-related activities. From a young age, children observe and mimic the

work of adults. Encouraging and supporting this interest in labor is essential for early development. The effectiveness of labor education at school is directly influenced by the foundation laid during preschool years. Children assist in household chores within their capacity – sweeping, tending crops or animals, helping with market errands, and caring for younger siblings. These everyday responsibilities should be nurtured and connected with respect for adult professions.

Labor is generally divided into two types: physical labor and mental labor. Tasks involving manual efforts fall under physical labor. However, meaningful physical work is only possible with intellectual input – whether hoeing, driving a tractor, or assembling parts in a factory, quality results depend on cognitive engagement. Mental labor, by contrast, is embodied by teachers, doctors, scientists, writers, and publishers. While physical labor sustains material well-being, mental labor enriches spiritual and intellectual life. Students themselves are intellectual laborers, as they continuously read, write, and think to build their inner world.

In school and society, students participate in physical labor as well – through physical education classes that promote health, and through community efforts such as cleaning classrooms or gardening. These shared responsibilities foster morality, discipline, and teamwork.

Forms and Methods of Labor Education

1. Labor Education in the Family

Parents, envisioning their children's future, must instill a work ethic from an early age. Work is one of the most effective forms of moral education. Every family has its own micro-economy built on honest labor. Instilling thriftiness in children ensures long-term benefits for themselves and society. One critical educational mistake is when parents satisfy every demand of their children without question. Instead, the following pedagogical guidelines should be observed:

- Children should be made aware of where their parents work and the social value of their work.
- Children should be introduced early to the family budget. Even if financial conditions are favorable, they should not be allowed to boast or develop pride in comparison to their peers.
- Parents must model and monitor honesty, integrity, and sincerity. Children should be taught not to take what does not belong to them, even if it is within reach.
- Thrift and prudence should be practiced at home – extending the life of worn items, managing household repairs, and budgeting are lessons in real-world economics.
- Children must learn to care for their own belongings as well as those of others.
- Saving and responsible spending should be introduced through small-scale practices at home.
- Parents must lead by example, showing diligence and care in their own labor.
- Information from media – TV, radio, newspapers – as well as guidance from elders reinforces these values.

To implement labor education effectively within the family, the following pedagogical principles should be followed:

1. Labor should match the child's developmental abilities and include playful elements.
2. Tasks should be structured and regular.
3. Effort must be acknowledged to promote emotional satisfaction.
4. The example of parents and joint family work is vital.
5. Assignments should progress from simple and engaging to more complex and essential.
6. Educational value must be embedded in each task.
7. Children must not be punished with labor or rewarded with money – both approaches are counterproductive.

2. Labor Education in the School System

Children express an interest in work from an early age, and by the time they enter school, they often possess basic skills. These abilities are further developed through structured school-based instruction. Labor education at school builds work culture, responsibility, time management, and material efficiency. Students learn to use tools properly, avoid waste, and value the final product. Primary school teachers play a central role in nurturing these habits by utilizing various educational tools and integrating labor values into daily lessons.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Economic education is a critical component in preparing young people to make independent and informed decisions within a market economy. Teaching economic knowledge to students in grades 5–6 of secondary schools – both in theoretical and practical dimensions – contributes to the development of their financial literacy, entrepreneurial skills, and thriftiness. Legislative and strategic initiatives in Uzbekistan, such as the 2022 resolution “On Improving the Economic Education System”, provide strong institutional support for research and implementation in this field.

The findings of the study indicate that the effectiveness of economic education is determined by the following key factors:

1. Integrated approach – Economic concepts should be taught in conjunction with related subjects such as geography, mathematics, and labor education, creating interdisciplinary connections that reinforce understanding.
2. Practical orientation – Incorporating projects, business simulations, and exercises in resource management enhances students' real-world application of economic knowledge.
3. Family-school collaboration – The involvement of parents is essential in shaping students' attitudes toward thrift, responsibility, and sound financial behavior from an early age.

List of the Literature:

1. Mandell, L. (2008). The impact of personal finance education delivered in high school and college courses. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 29(3), 418–440.
2. Walstad, W. B., Watts, M., & Rebeck, K. (2007). Does teaching economics affect students' attitudes toward the environment? *Journal of Economic Education*, 38(3), 281–293.
3. Murphy, L., & Moreno, A. (2018). Integrating economics in the elementary classroom: A study of teacher professional development and curriculum implementation. *Journal of Economic Education*, 49(3), 258–270.
4. Wise, S., & Reardon, M. (2016). Assessing the impact of a K–12 financial education program. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 37(3), 439–450.
5. Bandias, S., & Thapa, G. (2019). Incorporating economic concepts in mathematics instruction for young learners: A qualitative analysis of elementary teachers' experiences. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 95, 1–10.
6. Turakhanov, O. D. Theoretical foundations of economic education for 5–6 grade students of general education schools. *Academic International Conference on Multi-Disciplinary Studies and Education*. Hosted from Pittsburgh, USA, pp. 33–35.
7. Turaxanov, O. D. (2023). Umumta'lim maktablarining 5–6-sinf o'quvchilariga iqtisodiy tarbiya berishning asosiy mezonlari. *Journal of New Century Innovations*, 34(1), 140–143. <http://www.newjournal.org/>

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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